

SUPPLEMENT 5. Chinese scientific names of the new species, new combination and newly recorded species in China described in this study.

Scientific Names

Latin	Chinese (Pinyin and note bracketed)
<i>Hymenagaricus splendidissimus</i>	华丽层蘑菇 (huá lì céng mó gū) (新拟)
<i>Xanthagaricus boluoshanensis</i>	菠萝山黄蘑菇 (bō luó shān huáng mó gū) (新拟)
<i>Xanthagaricus chamaeleontinus</i>	变色龙黄蘑菇 (biàn sè lóng huáng mó gū) (新拟)
<i>Xanthagaricus erinaceus</i>	刺猬黄蘑菇 (cì wèi huáng mó gū) (新拟)
<i>Xanthagaricus guangzhouensis</i>	广州黄蘑菇 (guǎng zhōu huáng mó gū) (新拟)
<i>Xanthagaricus heinemannii</i>	海氏黄蘑菇 (hǎi shì huáng mó gū) (新拟)
<i>Xanthagaricus minimus</i>	迷你黄蘑菇 (mí nǐ huáng mó gū) (新拟)
<i>Xanthagaricus necopinatus</i>	奇迹黄蘑菇 (qí jì huáng mó gū) (新拟)
<i>Xanthagaricus phylononcaeruleus</i>	无理黄蘑菇 (wú lǐ huáng mó gū) (新拟)
<i>Xanthagaricus purpureosquamulosus</i>	紫鳞黄蘑菇 (zǐ lín huáng mó gū) (新拟)
<i>Xanthagaricus retisporus</i>	网孢黄蘑菇 (wǎng bào huáng mó gū) (新拟)
<i>Xanthagaricus scauinus</i>	华南农黄蘑菇 (huá nán nóng huáng mó gū) (新拟)